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1 INTRODUCTION

This report is a user guide to exploit the results, datasets and products elaborated and disseminated through the **EC-PROOF project “Estimation of Primary Production for Fisheries Management”**, within the marine food-chain, mass-balanced model system called Ecopath with Ecosim (Christensen *et al.*, 2000), hereafter referred to as EwE.

A short introduction about EwE is first given, with emphasised on the model parameters that can be provided by PROOF.

A review of datasets and products elaborated within PROOF is then given, together with a presentation of the interactive web-based system, which has been implemented in order to ease the access to the voluminous amount of data produced within PROOF.

Then, practical guidelines are proposed in order to use PROOF products as efficiently as possible in connection with EwE.

2 REQUIREMENTS FOR DATA IN EWE

The requirements from Ecopath with Ecosim – EwE are presented in details in PROOF report “D1: Proof-of-concept”. Only the main conclusions of this report will be recalled hereafter. For further details please access D1 report at <http://www.nersc.no/PROOF>.

Ecopath with Ecosim is designed to help constructing regional or basin scale models of the trophic flows in the marine ecosystem. Such models give an overview of the feeding interactions in the ecosystem, and of the resources it contains. Ecopath allows analyzing the marine ecosystem in details, and through Ecosim one can simulate effects of changes in fishing pressure, and, given time series data, evaluate the relative impact of fisheries and environment.

2.1 Parameterisation of the lowest trophic level in EwE

Ecopath bases the parameterisation on an assumption of mass balance over an arbitrary period, usually one year. In its present implementation Ecopath parameterises (version 4) models based on two master-equations, one to describe the production term and one for the energy balance of each trophic group.

The production term for each group (i) is split in components. This is implemented with the following equation

$$P_i = Y_i + B_i + M2_i + E_i + BA_i + P_i \cdot (1 - EE_i) \quad (2.1)$$

where P_i is the total production rate of compartment (i), Y_i is the total fishery catch rate of (i), $M2_i$ is the total predation rate for group (i), B_i the biomass of the group, E_i the net migration rate (emigration - immigration), BA_i is the biomass accumulation rate for (i), while $M0_i = P_i \cdot (1 - EE_i)$ is the other mortality rate for (i).

For parameterisation Ecopath sets up a system with (at least in principle) as many linear equations as there are groups in a system, and it solves the set for one of the following parameters for each group:

- biomass;

- production/biomass ratio;
- consumption/biomass ratio; or
- ecotrophic efficiency.

Energy balance is ensured within each group using the equation:

$$\text{Consumption} = \text{production} + \text{respiration} + \text{unassimilated food} \quad (2.2)$$

In Ecopath, the energy balance is performed so as to estimate respiration from the difference between consumption and the production and unassimilated food terms.

Ecopath can work with energy- (which imply a respiration term) as well as with nutrient-related (which imply no respiration term) currencies. Only models constructed using an energy-related currency ($\text{t}\cdot\text{km}^2\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$) can be run under Ecosim and Ecospace. If a nutrient based currency is used in Ecopath the respiration term is excluded from the above equation, and the unassimilated food term is estimated as the difference between consumption and production.

Most, if not all, Ecopath models constructed so far have initially been based on a single set of input parameters representing the mean for the model period, typically for a given year. The model constructor typically modifies the input parameters so as to obtain mass balance, and the outcome is a possible model of how the trophic model in the system may have been during the given year. “Possible” in this context means that basic physiological and thermodynamic constraints are considered, but also that it is just one of many possible representations of the flows in the ecosystem.

To account for natural variability, a resampling routine, Ecoranger, has been designed to accept input probability distributions for the biomasses, consumption and production rates, ecotrophic efficiencies, catch rates, and diet compositions. The Ecoranger module allows entry of a range and mean/mode values for all the basic parameters, i.e., for the biomasses, consumption rates, production rates, ecotrophic efficiencies, and all elements of the diet compositions.

The following units can be used as energy-related quantities:

- Joules/ m^2
- kcal/ m^2
- g Carbon/ m^2
- g / m^2 (dry weight)

- t / km^2 (wet weight)

If a nutrient-related unit is chosen, it may be expressed either as $mg N / m^2$ or $mg P / m^2$.

2.2 Initialisation of the temporal simulation module in EwE

Ecosim provides a dynamic simulation capability at the ecosystem level, with key initial parameters inherited from the base Ecopath model. The key computational aspects are in summary form: .

- Use of mass-balance results (from Ecopath) for parameter estimation;
- Variable speed splitting enables efficient modelling of the dynamics of both fast. (phytoplankton) and slow groups (whales). Effects of micro-scale behaviours on macro-scale rates: top-down vs. bottom-up control is incorporated explicitly;
- Includes biomass and size structure dynamics for key ecosystem groups.

Forcing function in Ecosim

In Ecosim, it is possible to apply forcing functions that constrain the behaviour of the system at each time step. Different seasonal and long-term shape functions can be defined and then assign to different trophic groups for constraining the behaviour of these groups on two time scale, typically monthly and yearly time-scale (Figure 1 & Figure 2).

Figure 1. Defining seasonal and long-term forcing functions

Prey \ predator	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1 Apex predators											
2 Juv. predators	0										
3 Epipelagic nekt	0	0		0							
4 Mesopelagics	0	0	0	0							
5 Bathypelagics					0						
6 Benthic fish						4					
7 Benthos					0	0	0				
8 Zooplankt.large	0	0	0	0	0						
9 Phytoplankton			1						1	1	1
10 MicroZooplankt.			0	0					0		
11 Detritus					0	0	0				

Figure 2. Assigning forcing functions to trophic groups

2.3 Set up of spatio-temporal simulations in EwE

The major deficiency of the Ecopath/Ecosim approach is its assumption of homogenous spatial behaviour. This has been remedied through the development of Ecospace (Walters *et al.* 1999), a dynamic, spatial version of Ecopath, incorporating all key elements of Ecosim. Ecospace dynamically allocates biomass across a grid map. In essence, it incorporates an Ecosim model in each spatial, non-land cell. Exchange between spatial cells is modelled for each time step (typically monthly), while accounting for food availability, predation and fishing patterns. The Ecospace model is constructed based on general information about habitat and depth preferences for the functional groups of the ecosystems.

3 THE PROOF DATASETS

In this section, the datasets and products developed and implemented in PROOF are presented, as well as the web-based interface that gives access to users for browsing and extracting information from the PROOF database.

3.1 Available data

PROOF provides two main datasets, respectively based on remote sensing data (SeaWiFS) and on 3-D ecosystem model simulations (the Nansen Center DIADEM and HYCOM ocean circulation and ecosystem models).

3.1.1 Remote sensing dataset

The basic quantity derived from satellite ocean colour data that can sustain the estimation of required parameters in EwE is the concentration of chlorophyll-a in the phytoplankton community. A detailed explanation of methods and optical model used to derive chlorophyll-a concentration from satellite data is presented in PROOF-D3 “Remote Sensing Algorithms”.

Satellite-derived chlorophyll concentration can be further used as an input parameter in primary production models, which aim at deriving the production of the lowest trophic level, i.e. phytoplankton. The model adopted to derive primary production from satellite Earth observation data is presented in PROOF-D3 and D4 “Validated Production Line”.

Primary production maps (in $\text{mg C m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$) at 9 or 18-km resolution are available at different spatial and temporal scales:

- monthly, seasonally and annually averaged maps covering the year from 1997 to 2002.
- climatology product corresponding to the average over the six years interval covered by the project.
- global (worldwide), North Atlantic, Europe, Celtic Sea and English Channel.

Additional models can be used to estimate the phytoplankton biomass from chlorophyll concentration and other data. A conversion model proposed to derive phytoplankton biomass from pigment biomass was presented in PROOF-D1 “Proof-of-Concept”. However, since such conversion models have a limited reliability, estimate of phytoplankton biomass derived from remote-sensing data has not been considered as a standard product within the PROOF project.

Based on the operational methods developed in PROOF, several types of satellite-derived information can be used as input parameters in EwE:

- primary production
- seasonal and annual variability of the above parameters (for annual simulation in the Ecosim module)
- spatial distribution of these parameters (for accounting for ecosystem habitats in the Ecospace module)

Based on the methods suggested and according to available parameterisation units in EwE, it seems reasonable to adopt a carbon-related unit for the integration of satellite-derived quantities in the food-chain model.

3.1.2 Model output

PROOF uses a state-of-the-art 3-D coupled physical-biogeochemical model (see PROOF-D8 “Model Validation”) in order to simulate a number of parameters, which can be used either within the primary production algorithm or as direct products for EwE’s users.

The basic quantities derived from the model that can be used in connection with the estimation of primary production from remotely sensed chlorophyll *a* are:

- the vertical (depth) distribution of phytoplankton biomass;
- the vertical (depth) profile of water temperature;
- the mixed layer depth, which can be used to estimate the water layer where primary production is concentrated.

These outputs have been produced for PROOF as weekly values, and seasonal and annual average (PROOF-D6 and D7 – a merged database tool).

The basic quantities derived from the model of relevance in EwE are:

- the phytoplankton biomass (expressed as $\text{mmol N}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$);

- the 3-D spatial distribution of phytoplankton and zooplankton and detritus to be used within Ecospace;
- the temporal variability of the above parameters to be used within Ecosim.

These outputs have been made available at the PROOF web-site http://www.nersc.no/~proof/proof_products.html.

Fluxes of nitrogen between the nutrient compartments (nitrate and ammonium) and the phytoplankton may be used to assess the uptake of nitrogen by primary producer and hence to derive an estimate of the primary production.

Based to the model parameterisation and according to available parameterisation units in EwE, it seems reasonable to adopt a nitrogen-related unit for the integration of model-derived quantities in the food-chain model.

3.2 Web-based interactive access

In order to enable the results of PROOF to be disseminated as widely and efficiently as possible the data have been interfaced to the internet through the PROOF world-wide web site (<http://www.nersc.no/PROOF>). Access to the remote sensing data is currently restricted since the primary production maps were derived from SeaWiFS data which cannot be used for commercial work in line with NASA's research agreement with the satellite's owners, Orbital Sciences Inc.

Figure 3. PROOF website “gallery” showing monthly Primary Production maps for 2000 Europe area

Figure 3 above shows the web site in “gallery” mode i.e. with all data for a given year; images can also be viewed for just single months. Clicking on “Extract” under each image leads to the data extraction interface shown in Figure 4. This has a number of options: data can be extracted by specifying a latitude/longitude point, or alternatively by moving a cursor over the production image.

In addition to the main overview there is a zoom window with X1, X2, X4 and X4 magnification. It is also possible to construct a list of geographical positions that allow extraction from each image viewed, and hence the construction of a time series. Finally, the mean production for all valid pixels in a 3x3 box centred on the pixel of interest is calculated along with a standard deviation.

Primary Production for Fisheries Management (PROOF)
 Extracting values from Monthly image for May 2000 (Europe)

Year: 1997 | 1998 | 1999 | 2000 | 2001 | 2002
 Month: January | February | March | April | May | June | July | August | September | October | November | December

Calculated Primary production at 50.147°N 9.673°W is 2615.17 $\text{mg C m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$

Click on either of the images below extract a value

Region View

Detail view

Zoom: 1 | 2 | 4 | 8

200 300 400 500 700 900 2000 3000 5000 7000
 $\text{mg C m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$

Enter a Latitude/Longitude

Latitudes and longitudes should be entered in decimal degree form, with negative values being South or West.

Latitude: Longitude:

Add To List (Select this if you wish to add the location to the list of extracted locations)

Extract Reset

Statistics in 3x3 box:

- Valid samples: 9
- Mean: 2273.35 $\text{mg C m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$
- Standard deviation: 196.97 $\text{mg C m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$

Add this location to the list of extracted locations.

List of Extracted Locations			
Latitude	Longitude	Primary Production / $\text{mg C m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$	Remove Point
60.000°N	13.366°W	1851.4	Remove
46.979°N	3.869°W	1141.56	Remove
50.147°N	9.673°W	2615.17	Remove
Remove All			

Period: Month | Season | Annual
 Region: Global | Atlantic | North Atlantic | Celtic Sea | English Channel | Europe

Click here for the [climatological values](#).
 Click [here](#) for the gallery.

Figure 4. Tool to extract primary production values from the PROOF maps.

4 USE OF PROOF DATASETS WITHIN ECOPATH

In this section, guidelines and recommendations are given for practical use and integration of PROOF dataset within EwE

4.1 Use of the remote sensing dataset

An interactive tool has been implemented in order extract from the dataset, primary production at the different time-scale available. While entering this extraction area, the web interface sets up in “monthly mode”, and the global coverage for January 2000 is displayed, as well as a zoom on the Gulf of Guinea (approx. 0°N, 0°E).

Primary Production for Fisheries Management (PROOF)
 Extracting values from Monthly image for January 2000 (Global)

Year: 1997 | 1998 | 1999 | **2000** | 2001 | 2002
 Month: **January** | February | March | April | May | June | July | August | September | October | November | December
 Calculated Primary production at 0.176°S 0.176°E is **1065.37** mg C m⁻² day⁻¹

Click on either of the images below extract a value

Region View Detail view

Zoom: 1 | 2 | 4 | 8

200 300 400 500 700 900 2000 3000 5000 7000
 mg C m⁻² day⁻¹

Enter a Latitude/Longitude
 Latitudes and longitudes should be entered in decimal degree form, with negative values being South or West.

Latitude: 0.176 Longitude: 0.176

Add To List (Select this if you wish to add the location to the list of extracted locations)

Extract Reset

Statistics in 3x3 box:

- Valid samples: 9
- Mean: 1186.61 mg C m⁻² day⁻¹
- Standard deviation: 111.71 mg C m⁻² day⁻¹

Add this location to the list of extracted locations.

Period: **Month** | Season | Annual

Region: **Global** | Atlantic | North Atlantic | Celtic Sea | English Channel | Europe

[Click here for the climatological values.](#)

[Click here for the gallery.](#)

Please note that the algorithm used in producing the primary production values is valid only in case 1 waters.

W3C CSS

Figure 5. Default webpage while accessing the extraction tool

The browser displays a calculated primary production at 0.176°S 0.176°E of 1065.37 mg C m⁻² day⁻¹.

The location can be changed by clicking on either the global map or the zoom image, or by entering coordinates in the appropriate windows (Figure 4).

A list of values pertaining to different locations can be easily created by activating the “add to list” button (see Figure 4).

In “monthly mode”, users have the possibility to select the year, month and geographic region of interest.

In “seasonal mode”, users have access to four maps corresponding to Spring, Summer, Autumn and Winter periods, respectively (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Browsing the PROOF satellite primary production dataset in “Seasonal mode”. Average primary production for spring 1999 is displayed on a global scale, together with a zoom on the Celtic Sea.

In “annual mode”, there is access to one of the six years processed in the course of PROOF.

Primary Production for Fisheries Management (PROOF)

Extracting values from Annual image for 2002 (North Atlantic)

Year: [1997](#) | [1998](#) | [1999](#) | [2000](#) | [2001](#) | **2002**

Calculated Primary production at 43.383°N 8.996°W is **703.88** mg C m⁻² day⁻¹

Click on either of the images below extract a value

<p>Region View</p> <p>Zoom: 1 2 4 8</p>	
--	---

mg C m⁻² day⁻¹

Enter a Latitude/Longitude

Latitudes and longitudes should be entered in decimal degree form, with negative values being South or West.

Latitude:	Longitude:
43.383	-8.996

Add To List (Select this if you wish to add the location to the list of extracted locations)

Statistics in 3x3 box:

- Valid samples: 9
- Mean: 759.29 mg C m⁻² day⁻¹
- Standard deviation: 88.84 mg C m⁻² day⁻¹

[Add this location to the list of extracted locations.](#)

Period: [Month](#) | [Season](#) | **[Annual](#)**

Region: [Global](#) | [Atlantic](#) | **[North Atlantic](#)** | [Celtic Sea](#) | [English Channel](#) | [Europe](#)

[Click here for the climatological values.](#)

[Click here for the gallery.](#)

Please note that the algorithm used in producing the primary production values is valid only in case 1 waters.

Figure 7. Browsing the PROOF satellite primary production dataset in “annual mode”. Example for 2002, centred on the North Atlantic, and zoomed on the Galician shelf.

Climatology, calculated over the six years of processed data, is also available. Monthly climatology for the Celtic Sea and seasonal climatology for the North Atlantic are presented in Figure 8 and Figure 9, respectively.

Figure 8. Monthly primary production climatology for the Celtic Sea, estimated from SeaWiFS-derived chlorophyll a data and using the PROOF primary production model.

Figure 9. Seasonal primary production climatology for the North Atlantic, estimated from SeaWiFS-derived chlorophyll a data and using the PROOF primary production model.

4.1.1 Computing annual primary production

Monthly, seasonal and annual estimates of primary production have been calculated from daily SeaWiFS images and then averaged over the different periods of time. They are provided in unit of $\text{mgC}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$.

However most EwE ecosystem/regional models are mass-balanced over a period of one year. Therefore primary production is to be provided in unit of $\text{t C}/\text{km}^2/\text{yr}$.

For regions or ecosystems with limited seasonal variability, one can calculate a usable estimate by applying the following relationship:

$$PP \text{ (tC/km}^2\text{/yr)} = PP \text{ (mgC/m}^2\text{/day)} * 0.365 \quad (4.1)$$

Otherwise, it is preferred to use monthly estimates as followed:

$$PP \text{ (t C/km}^2\text{/yr)} = 10^{-3} * [(PP_jan * 31) + (PP_Feb * 28) + \dots + (PP_Dec * 31)] \quad (4.2)$$

4.1.2 Deriving seasonal variability pattern

Seasonal variability pattern for a specific year or as climatology, can be produced by browsing each month for the same location. This is made easy since the definition of the location is kept as defaults when displaying data for specific months.

Twelve values can thus be extracted. Any plotting software can then be used to produce the variability pattern needed for the seasonal forcing of the primary producer in Ecosim (Figure 1).

Figure 10 presents an example of realistic seasonal forcing functions obtained from a time series of PROOF primary production covering the spring bloom period in 1998 and 1999 for the Celtic Sea.

Figure 10. Seasonal variability pattern derived from primary production monthly-averaged maps.

4.1.3 Defining spatial grid in Ecospace

An example of efficient use of satellite-derived productivity for accounting for spatial variability in the Ecospace module, has been investigated by Christensen *et al.* (2001). Although yet no example has been elaborated using the datasets produced in PROOF, the methodology proposed by these authors is briefly described below, is directly applicable to PROOF datasets.

Ecospace (Walters *et al.* 1999), a dynamic, spatial version of Ecopath, incorporates all key elements of Ecosim, and allows the dynamical allocation of biomass across a grid map.

Ecospace, in essence, incorporates an Ecosim model in each spatial, non-land cell – of which there are for instance 369 in the North Sea model represented in the right panel of Figure 11.

Figure 11: Patterns of annual primary production in the North Sea at two different resolutions scaling from high at the coasts in southeast to low in the central parts of the area. The left panel shows estimated productivity at a one-sixth degree scale based on SeaWiFS data, as made available by the EU Joint Research Centre. The right panel shows how this information is averaged, scaled to the original mean, and represented using 1 by 1 degree cells in the Ecospace models of the North Sea. The demise of the Shetland Islands is unintentional, and reflects a consequence of using a coarse map.

The above Ecospace models were constructed based on general information about habitat and depth preferences for the functional groups of the ecosystems. Primary production was distributed spatially based on SeaWiFS data as described below.

For each of the spatial model the cells were distributed between habitats based on depth only. The following depth strata were used for all models: (1) <10 m; (2) 11-50 m; (3) 51-100 m, (4) 101-200 m; (5) 201-1000 m, (6): >1000 m. Depth information at the 0.5 by 0.5 degree scale was obtained from the ETOPO5 data set available on the U.S. National Geophysical Data Center's Global Relief Data CD

(www.ngdc.noaa.gov/products/ngdc_products.html) as implemented in the *Sea Around Us* project database (<http://www.fisheries.ubc.ca/projects/saup>), and obtained by linking Ecospace to a GIS system, see Figure 12A.

The predicted distributions in Ecospace models show marked sensitivity to primary productivity patterns, and these have in general not been well described in previous Ecospace models. To improve on this, one can use primary productivity maps based on SeaWiFS data. (Figure 12B).

Figure 12 (A) Depth, (B) yearly averaged primary production and (C) yearly averaged temperature (at 10 m depth) in the North Atlantic. The depths scale from light being low depth to dark being deep. Primary Production (B) scales from light being low productivity to dark representing high productivity. The temperatures are coldest (blue) in the arctic region, and the color scale is linear.

Temperatures at 10 meters depth were obtained from climatology based on the NOAA World Ocean Atlas 1998 (www.nodc.noaa.gov/OC5/wod98v2.html), as implemented in the *Sea Around Us* project database (see Figure 12.C).

In PROOF, water temperature maps and depth is provided through the couple ocean ecosystem model simulations (see section 3.1.2).

4.2 Use of the *DIADEM/HYCOM* model output

The *DIADEM* model has been run in reduced vertical resolution (*MICOM*) mode from 1995 to 1998, and in high vertical resolution (*HYCOM*) mode from 1997 to 1998. Examples of simulated phytoplankton seasonal variability are presented in Figure 13 and Figure 15.

Figure 13: Phytoplankton biomass and seasonal variability simulated by the DIADEM model (February to August).

The depth-profile presented in Figure 15 follows a curvilinear line (shown in Figure 14), which approximately covers the two regions of interest in PROOF, namely the Celtic Sea and the Northern Iberian shelf.

Figure 14: Selected transect for the depth profile plots (Figure 15)

Figure 15: Phytoplankton biomass depth-profile (Seasonal variability).

A web-based user interface has been implemented in order to ease access to the specific portions of the modelled dataset, as well as to ease extracting EwE-type parameters (mixed layer depth, and vertical profiles of temperature and phytoplankton concentration) data input. The values can be extracted as weekly, monthly or seasonal values from the 1997 model simulations. The parameter values are extracted in tabular form for use in EwE for a selected location (either through input of lat/long or for a pointing on the map locations) and plotted as vertical profiles for the phytoplankton and temperature. Time series (weekly, monthly or seasonal) of the surface phytoplankton values can also be extracted and plotted for given locations. Figure 16 shows the graphical interface for extraction of the modelled parameters developed in PROOF for use in EwE simulations.

Figure 16: Browsing the PROOF model simulated dataset of the mixed layer depth, vertical temperature distribution and phytoplankton concentration in “Seasonal mode” for 1997. The bathymetry is shown on the graphical map of the Atlantic Ocean, which also can be used for data extraction.

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